

Mathematical validation of helix coil transition in polypeptides : A modelling approach

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Abstract : Helix Coil transition is mathematically analysed through binomial and geometric expansion series. The model related to helix coil transition like Zipper and Zimm-Bragg model are validated mathematically and the physical properties like stability parameter, microscopic equilibrium constant and the degree of conversion are modelled by computational method.

Keywords : Helix Coil transition, Zipper model, Zimm-Bragg model, degree of conversion.

Proteins are polymers that attain well defined three dimensional structures both in solution and in biological cells. They are polypeptides, formed from different amino acids strung together by the peptide link -CONH- hydrogen bonds between amino acids of a polypeptide give rise to stable helical or sheet structures, which may collapse into a random coil when certain conditions are changed. For example, the synthetic polypeptide poly- γ -benzyl glutamate is helical in a non-hydrogen bonding solvent, but in a hydrogen bonding solvent it forms a random coil. The unwinding of helix into a random coil is a cooperative transition^{1,2}, in which polymer becomes more susceptible to structural changes once the process have begun. In their pioneer work the influence of the hydrodynamic interaction on the folding process in minimal protein model was studied by Baum-Ketner and Hiwatari³. This effective interaction is accounted in their simulations through tensor analysis. Both thermodynamic and kinetic properties of the examined models were studied by using Brownian dynamic simulations³. It was found that the effect of hydrodynamic interaction on the folding process of a protein depends on the geometry of its native state.

The present work involves the mathematical analysis of the models grounded in the principle of statistical

thermodynamics that accounts for the cooperativity⁴ of the helix-coil transition of polypeptide through binomial and geometric expansion series and finally validated by computational procedure by a standard software programming language like (C++).

To calculate the fraction of polypeptide molecules present as helix or coil we need to set-up the partition function for the various states of the molecule. We could attempt a calculation of the electronic, vibrational and rotational contributions to the molecular partition function of the entire polypeptide. This molecule is too large for this approach to be feasible. Instead of this approach, the partition function in terms of equilibrium constants for transitions between different states of polypeptide chains is adopted.

Discussion and results^{4,5}

To start with consider a short polypeptide chain with four amino acid residues, each labelled *h* if it contributes to a helical region and *c* if it contributes to a random coil region. We suppose that the conformations *hhh* and *ccc* contribute terms $q_0({}^4C_0)$ and $({}^4C_4)q_4$, respectively, to the partition function *q*.

Then we assume the following steps :

- (i) Each of the four conformations with one c amino acid (such as $hchh$) contributes $q_1({}^4C_1)$.
- (ii) Similarly, each of the four states with two c amino acids contributes a term $q_2({}^4C_2)$.
- (iii) Each of the four states with three c amino acids contributes a term $q_3({}^4C_3)$.

The partition function of polypeptide of four amino acids is then,

$$\begin{aligned} q &= ({}^4C_0)q_0 + ({}^4C_1)q_1 + ({}^4C_2)q_2 + ({}^4C_3)q_3 + ({}^4C_4)q_4 \\ &= q_0 + 4q_1 + 6q_2 + 4q_3 + q_4 \\ q_0 &= \left(1 + \frac{4q_1}{q_0} + \frac{6q_2}{q_0} + \frac{4q_3}{q_0} + \frac{q_4}{q_0}\right) \end{aligned}$$

The equilibrium constant $K_n = q_n/q_0$ between the conformation hhh and one of the conformations of composition $C^n h^{4-n}$.

$$\therefore q = q_0(1 + 4K_1 + 6K_2 + 4K_3 + K_4)$$

Now, we suppose the conformational transition from ($C^n h^{4-n} \rightarrow C^{n+1} h^{3-n}$)

i.e. helical to random coil transformation occurs as following :

As equilibrium constant K_n is related to Gibb's free energy change (ΔG^0) standard state at a particular temperature T becomes,

$$K_n = \exp(-n\Delta G^0/RT) = K_1^n$$

where $K_1 = \exp(-\Delta G^0/RT)$

\therefore The partition function becomes,

$$q = q_0(1 + 4K_1 + 6K_1^2 + 4K_1^3 + K_1^4)$$

For helix coil transition or cooperative transition K_1 is denoted as s so,

$$q = q_0(1 + 4s + 6s^2 + 4s^3 + s^4) = q_0(1 + s)^4$$

By applying binomial expansion

$$q/q_0 = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^4 c(4,i)s^i \quad (1)$$

The coefficient $c(4,i)$ is the number of ways in which a state with i , c amino acids can be formed.

For a longer polypeptide chain four may be replaced by N . Therefore eq. (1) becomes,

$$q/q_0 = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^N c(N,i)s^i \quad (2)$$

For a polypeptide with n amino acids, the partition function (q) becomes,

$$q = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^n N_i s^i \quad (3)$$

where N_i is the number of ways in which a state with a number i of c amino acids can be formed.

There are many ways in which a long polypeptide can change from a helix to random coil. The simplest way to visualise the process is to use the **Zipper model**, in which a conversion from h to c is allowed only if an amino acid adjacent to the one undergoing conversion is already a c amino acid.

Cooperativity is included in the Zipper model by assuming the first conversion from h to c , called the nucleation step, is less favourable than the remaining conversions and has microscopic equilibrium constant σs , where $\sigma s \ll 1$. Each subsequent step is called a propagation step and has a microscopic equilibrium constant s . Calculations based on more complete model, known as **Zimm-Bragg model**, give the following expression for θ .

$$\theta = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \frac{(s-1) + 2\sigma}{\sqrt{(s-1)^2 + 4s\sigma}} \right] \quad (4)$$

A plot of θ against s for several values of s shows a sigmoidal shape characteristics of cooperative behaviour.

Introducing the microscopic equilibrium constant σs in eq. (3) we get,

$$q = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^n N_i \sigma s^i \quad (5)$$

where N_i is the number of ways in which q state with a number i of c amino acids can be formed under the structures of the Zipper model.

$$\therefore N_i = (n - i + 1) \quad (6)$$

By putting the value of $N_i = (n - i + 1)$ in eq. (5)

$$q = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^n (n - i + 1) \sigma s^i \quad (7)$$

The following eqs. (8) to (19) may be considered as output equations by following sets of mathematical operations as follows.

$$q = 1 + \sigma(n+1) \sum_{i=1}^n s^i - \sigma \sum_{i=1}^n i s^i \quad (8)$$

Evaluating the two geometric series as follows,

$$\sum_{i=1}^n s^i = s + s^2 + s^3 + \dots + s^n$$

Here first them = s and common ratio = s

$$\therefore \sum_{i=1}^n s^i = \frac{s(s^n - 1)}{(s - 1)} = \frac{s^{n+1}}{(s - 1)} \quad (9)$$

Expanding each term,

For $i = 1$,

$$s + 2s^2 = \frac{s(2s + 1)(s - 1)^2}{(s - 1)^2} = \frac{s(2s^3 - 3s^2 + 1)}{(s - 1)^2}$$

For $i = 3$,

$$s + 2s^2 + 2s^3 = \frac{s(1 + 2s + 3s^2)(s - 1)^2}{(s - 1)^2} = \frac{s(3s^3 - 4s^3 + 1)}{(s - 1)^2}$$

For $i = n$,

$$s + 2s^2 + 3s^3 + \dots + ns^n = \frac{s}{(s - 1)^2} \{ns^{n+1} - (n + 1)s^n + 1\}$$

$$\therefore \sum is^i = \frac{s}{(s - 1)^2} \{ns^{n+1} - (n + 1)s^n + 1\} \quad (10)$$

After putting the values of $\sum_{i=1}^n s^i$ and $\sum_{i=1}^n is^i$, the eq. (6) becomes,

$$q = 1 + \frac{\sigma s [s^{n+1} - (n + 1)s^n + 1]}{(s - 1)^2} \quad (11)$$

The fraction $p_i = q_i/q$ of molecules that has a number i of c amino acids is

$$p_i = [(n - i + 1)\sigma s^i]/q \quad (12)$$

and the mean value of i is then $\langle i \rangle = \sum_i ip_i$ (13)

The degree of conversion, θ of a polypeptide with n amino acids to random coil is defined as,

$$\theta = \frac{\langle i \rangle}{n} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n ip_i}{n} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (n - i + 1) i \sigma s^i}{nq} \quad (14)$$

Rearrangement of eq. (12) gives;

$$\sum_{i=1}^n (n - i + 1) i \sigma s^i = (n\theta)q \quad (15)$$

Applying differential operator with respect to s on eq. (3) we get,

$$\frac{dq}{ds} = \sum_{i=1}^n N_i \sigma i s^{i-1} = \frac{1}{s} \sum_{i=1}^n N_i i \sigma s^i = \frac{1}{s} \sum_{i=1}^n (n - i + 1) i \sigma s^i = \frac{q}{s} (n\theta) \quad (16)$$

$$\therefore \frac{dq}{q} = n\theta \left(\frac{ds}{s} \right) \quad (17)$$

$$\theta = \frac{1}{n} \frac{d(\ln q)}{d(\ln s)} \quad (18)$$

By solving the eq. (16) we get,

$$q = A s^{n\theta} \quad (19)$$

(where A = integration constant).

The eq. (19) is the most important modelling relationship for **any model of helix coil transition** where the partition function q is expressed as a function of stability parameter s and degree of conversion (θ).

The eq. (4) represents θ as a function of σ and s . The following results are obtained by computational validation⁶ of eq. (4).

The execution of the programme is tabulated as follows in the form of standard output.

The results obtained are as follows.

Output :

Enter data index : 04

Enter the value of microscopic equilibrium constant (sig) : 0.05

Enter the value of stability parameter (s) :
0.8, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0

The value of degree of conversion (th) :
0.388197, 0.611803, 0.90452, 0.964835

This model is validated by $n = 20$ amino acid residues with the standard data⁴ of $s = 0.8, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0$ for the standard polypeptide like poly- γ -benzyl glutamate. The increase in value of θ with increase in value of s signifies that the greater probability of helix to random coil in a hydrogen bonding solvent. Since the algorithm is developed through array variable⁶, so the standard programme can be executed by large numbers of data index. In addition to the poly- γ -benzyl glutamate, the above programme can be also executed to larger polypeptide if the standard data of σ and s are available. The eqs. (8) to (19) form the basis of calculating the important parameters like partition function, microscopic equilibrium constant, stability parameters and finally the degree of conversion theoretically.

Experimental

The Experimental part of this work includes the computational validation of Zimm-Bragg model. The algorithm developed by an object oriented programming language⁶ like C++ (tC++, V.4.5) as follows :

```
# include <iostream.h>
```

```
void main <void>
```

```
{
```

```
float s[100], th[100];
```

```

float x[100], y[100];
float sig;
cout << "Enter Data Index : " << endl;
cin >> n;
cout << "Enter the value of Microscopic Equilibrium
constant (sig) : " << endl;
for (int i=0; i <= n; i++)
{
    cin >> s [i];
    x[i]=(s[i]-1)+2*sig;
    y[i]=((s[i]-1)*(s[i]-1)-4*sig*s[i]);
    th[i]=0.5*(1+x[i]/y[i]);
}
for (int i=0; i<=n; i++)
{
    cout << "The value of degree of conversion
(th) : " << th[i]<<endl;
}
}

```

The input data like microscopic equilibrium constant (σ) and stability parameter (s) are taken from a sigmoidal curve⁴ of θ vs s .

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